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Annotation: The search for new ways and forms of organizing education has created a new term in the methodology of learning “modern lesson” as opposed to traditional lesson. The requirements of the subject of pedagogy for the lesson, the effectiveness of the pedagogical process is constantly growing and changing. In addition to non-traditional lessons, non-traditional teaching technologies are used in school practice in conjunction with modern teaching methods. The article discusses the use of modern teaching methods in teaching students in the primary grades.

Keywords: pedagogy, education, method, teacher, student, skill, ability, tool, education.

In independent Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the activities of teachers, their pedagogical skills, aimed at reforming the system of continuing education and the organization of the educational process on the basis of new state educational standards. Recommendations for the application of pedagogical technology in the teaching process, which have begun to take place in the pedagogical thinking of teachers working in the educational process, are very important for teachers. There is a growing interest in the use of interactive methods and information technology in education. One of the reasons for this is that so far in traditional education, students are taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, while the use of modern technology allows them to search for their own knowledge, independent learning and thinking, analysis doing so teaches them to draw even the final conclusions themselves. In this process, the teacher facilitates the development, formation, acquisition and upbringing of the individual, and at the same time serves as a manager, a guide [1]. One of the key areas in improving current teaching methods is the introduction of interactive teaching and learning methods. All science teachers, including primary school teachers, are increasingly using interactive methods in their teaching. As a result of the use of interactive methods, students develop the ability to think independently, analyze, draw conclusions, express their opinions, defend them reasonably, and develop healthy communication skills. Indeed, certain interpersonal relationships between students are inevitable and depend on the success of their learning activities. The skillful organization of student interaction based on learning materials is a powerful factor in increasing the effectiveness of educational activities in general. The transition to new textbooks in schools, the introduction of new subjects, especially in modern education, makes it necessary to solve modern problems of education. Since the primary lesson of the primary school students is the lesson, the specific features of the lesson are the work of the students under the guidance of the teacher with a group of regular students in a strictly defined order for a specified period of time. performance. As science and textbooks change, so do the methods and nature of science teaching. Therefore, modern educational technologies aimed at organizing the activities of students, the development of their abilities, quality knowledge through these activities are very relevant [2]. The appropriateness of using interactive forms of teaching is determined separately by the tasks of the whole lesson and its stages. There are many methods of interactive learning. By using interactive teaching methods in the classroom, we are creating new opportunities to establish interpersonal relationships through external communication,

primarily in the process of mastering learning materials. Interactive means that the interaction between teacher and students increases the effectiveness of the lesson, the student learns a new lesson through independent action, reflection, discussion, the student in the lesson independently of the set goal actively tries to find answers in small groups, that is, thinks, evaluates, writes, speaks and listens, and most importantly, actively participates. Students who understand the content of the task based on interactive methods will enter the learning process with unknowing interest. Not everything can be taught, putting the most important achievements of different disciplines on children's heads is not the power of teachers. It is more important to give children a "fisherman, not a fish", to teach them to acquire this knowledge, to teach them their intellectual, communicative, creative abilities, to form a scientific worldview. In a modern school lesson, all the key elements of the learning process interact: its goals, content, tools, methods, and forms of educational organization. The relevance of the work is that the current transition to new educational technologies depends on changes in the existence and development of society, which requires new approaches and methods to the education of young students. The object of research is the child and the learning process. The research topic is modern methods of teaching in primary school. The aim of the work is to study the methods of teaching in a modern school in primary schools. Objectives: Review the theoretical foundations of teaching methods; to study the peculiarities of some methods of teaching in a modern school; consider using them in lessons; 1. Classification of teaching methods. 1.1 The concept of teaching methods and their classification Teaching methods (Greek. "Way to something") - methods of interaction between teachers and students aimed at solving educational tasks is one of the main components of the learning process. If you do not use different methods, it will not be possible to achieve the goals and objectives of teaching. Teaching methods include not only methods, but also how to organize learning activities. And any method can be chosen for learning, it all depends on the goals he wants to achieve. Sometimes a certain method is required to achieve success in education, while others are ineffective, the methodology of organizing training in vocational education was studied by A. Khodjaboyev, Sh. Kasimov and others [3 ; 4; 5; 6; 7; 8]. Depending on the method of teaching: the purpose of the lesson; from the course stage; from the content of education; availability of textbooks; from the teacher's personality; Tasks of teaching methods, techniques and tools: Education; Purpose; Development; Education; Organizational Classification according to the source of knowledge. Oral teaching methods: it is used to prepare for the study of new material in the process of explaining, assimilating, generalizing and applying it. - Widely used in the formation of students' theoretical knowledge. Ensuring the exchange of information between teachers and students. - Facts and presentations are given in a ready form. There are not enough opportunities to solve the problem and solve the problem, to do creative work. Development of logical thinking, knowledge of independent activity. Story-events, processes, phenomena in nature, society, in the life of an individual, in a group of people. Management function training. Relevant functions: development, nurture, encouragement, control and correction. Pedagogical requirements: The didactic objectives of the lesson should be achieved: To present new material. In order to generalize. The basic concept of PbO is learning problems — the mental state of students' mental interactions, a group of students with a problem under the guidance of a teacher. A problem is a complex theoretical or practical question that involves a hidden contradiction and leads to different (often contradictory) positions in resolving it. Learning problems are characterized by: a) the type of conflict identified by the teacher together with

the students; b) there are known ways to solve such problems; c) lack of new data or theoretical knowledge; g) students' ability to complete the task. Problem situations are divided into a number of fundamentals, such as a field of scientific knowledge or a discipline (mathematics, history, psychology, etc.); new (new knowledge, methods of action, transfer of certain knowledge and methods of action to new conditions); level of problems (depending on the severity of the conflict). There are two tactics to build a problem situation: a) "from knowledge to problem". The transition from the scientific content of the problem to the "consumption" of ready-made achievements of science is not enough to develop students' independent research skills and abilities; b) "from problem to knowledge". Based on the subjective experience of the listeners included in the logic of solving scientific problems, the motivation to look for ways and means to solve it forms an active theme of purposeful cognitive activity.

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